

Characterisation of Some New Mixed Schiff Base Complexes by Nitration and Demetallation Study

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Preparation and reactions of some new mixed Schiff complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II), containing 2-OH-acetophenonate and 2-OH-propiophenonate moieties, have been described, followed by their characterisation with the help of elemental analysis, magnetic and spectral studies. Study of mixed ligand complexes containing nitrated products of above ketones and isolation of the free unsymmetrical Schiff base by the demetallation of the tetradentate Schiff base complex of Cu(II) have been carried out to further confirm the mixed nature of above complexes.

In our previous communications¹⁻⁶ we have reported the formation of mixed Schiff base complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II). The two ligands used were mainly orthohydroxy aromatic aldehyde and orthohydroxy aromatic ketone. In the present paper, mixed complexes of 2-hydroxy acetophenone and 2-hydroxy propiophenone with more similar coordinating tendencies have been studied. Mixed nature of the complexes has been further confirmed by nitration studies. Amine exchange reactions have been carried out on the mixed ligand complex.

Parent mixed imine Schiff base complex MLL' (I, R=H), where M=Cu(II) or Ni(II), LH=2-hydroxy acetophenonimine and L'H=2-hydroxy propiophenonimine, on treatment with alkylamine (methyl or ethyl amine) or diamine (ethylene or propylene diamine) gave transamination products (I, R=CH₃ or C₂H₅ and II).

I
M=Cu(II) or Ni(II)
R=H, CH₃ or C₂H₅

II
M=Cu(II) or Ni(II)
R=H or CH₃

In case of Cu(II) complex(I), reaction with ethanolamine or isopropanolamine gave tridentate ligand complex(III). 2-Hydroxy acetophenone forms the tridentate ligand complex and 2-hydroxy propiophenone part is knocked out.

III
R=H or CH₃

To confirm the mixed Schiff base complex formation, two more mixed complexes of Cu(II) were prepared, one containing unnitrated 2-hydroxy acetophenonimine and 3,5 dinitro 2-hydroxy propiophenonimine as ligands (IV a) and the other containing 3,5 dinitro 2-hydroxy acetophenonimine and unnitrated 2-hydroxy propiophenone imine as ligands (IV b).

IV
R=H or NO₂

Demetallation of the complex(II) was also carried out to isolate the unsymmetrical Schiff base (V).

Experimental

Methods and Material: Orthohydroxy aromatic ketones were prepared by the standard procedure⁷. As detailed earlier¹ complexes (I) were prepared by refluxing metal tetramine with one equivalent each of two ligands. Amine exchange reactions with mono and dialkyl amines were carried out by refluxing complex (I) with proper amines^{1,2}. This leads to the formation of complexes (I, R=CH₃ or C₂H₅ and II). Reaction of hydroxylamine on(I) leads to the formation of tridentate complex (III)⁶.

3,5 dinitro 2-hydroxy acetophenone and 3,5 dinitro 2-hydroxy propiophenone were prepared by the procedure described in literature⁸. The nitrated ligands were then used to prepare the mixed Schiff base complexes (IV), by reacting one equivalent of each ligand with Cu(II) tetramine complex under the same conditions as in the synthesis of complex (I).

Demetallation of tetradentate Schiff base complexes of Cu(II) :

2.0 g of dry unsymmetrical tetradentate Schiff base complex[II, M=Cu(II) and R=H] was suspended in 100 ml dry benzene taken in 250 ml two necked round bottom flask. Water condenser (carrying anhydrous CaCl₂ to prevent absorption of moisture) was fixed in vertical position in one neck and a slow stream of dry H₂S gas was bubbled

through the second neck of the above flask for about half an hour. The resulting yellow solution was filtered and concentrated in vacuum, when a yellow crystalline powder was obtained. This was recrystallised from a mixture of dry benzene and dry petroleum ether.

Tlc, spectral and magnetic studies were carried out as detailed in earlier publications¹⁻⁶. The analytical data have been presented in the Table.

Results and Discussion

Purified and dried complexes (I to III) gave a single spot on tlc plate and satisfactory metal and nitrogen analyses.

All the Cu(II) complexes are paramagnetic showing the presence of one unpaired electron. Slightly higher values of μ_{eff} of the present complexes than spin only value ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=1.73$ B.M.), can be attributed to spin orbit coupling⁹. The visible spectra show a broad band around 530 nm. This corresponds to the combination of the three close energy bands in a tetragonal structure.

Ni(II) square planar complexes are expected to be diamagnetic. However, one complex is found to be partially paramagnetic. Such observation was made in case of Ni(II) complexes of Schiff bases studied^{1,10,11} earlier. This can be attributed to

TABLE—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND ANALYTICAL DATA

No.	Complex*	Metal%		Nitrogen%		λ_{max}		μ_{eff}
		Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	(nm)		
1.	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ Cu(I)	18.39	18.80	8.10	7.93	530		1.82
2.	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ Ni(I)	18.67	18.54	8.22	8.14	535		Diamagnetic
3.	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cu(I, R=CH ₃)	16.41	16.65	7.22	7.13	540		1.80
4.	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ Ni(I, R=CH ₃)	15.33	15.57	7.32	7.46	520		Partial Paramagnetic
5.	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₂ Cu(I, R=C ₂ H ₅)	14.61	14.52	6.97	7.45	525		1.92
6.	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₂ Ni(I, R=C ₂ H ₅)	14.79	14.60	7.06	7.42	530		Diamagnetic
7.	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cu(II, R=H)	17.10	17.24	7.54	7.01	530		1.96
8.	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ Ni(II, R=H)	16.00	16.31	7.64	6.95	540		Diamagnetic
9.	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cu(II, R=CH ₃)	16.48	16.37	7.26	7.08	535		2.01
10.	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ Ni(II, R=CH ₃)	15.42	15.26	7.36	7.65	530		Diamagnetic
11.	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ NCu(III, R=H)	24.57	24.18	5.42	5.64	630		1.83
12.	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ Cu(III, R=CH ₃)	23.31	23.56	5.14	4.90	625		1.94
13.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ Cu(IVa)	14.60	14.78	21.17	20.65	540		1.92
14.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ Cu(IVb)	14.60	14.97	21.17	20.59	535		1.88
			C		H		N	
		Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	
15.	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ (V) Schiff base m.p. 188-189°C	73.54	73.64	7.10	7.22	9.03	8.87	

* Entries inside the brackets refer to structural formulae.

polymerization through the coordination of the oxygen atom of one complex at fifth and sixth positions of the other molecules, resulting in tetragonal structure. The paramagnetism is not due to partial tetrahedral distortion, because the visible spectrum of all Ni(II) complexes in solution show a shoulder at ~ 540 nm. There is no band beyond 640 nm showing that the structure is square planar. This shows that octahedral structure, due to polymerisation, breaks in solution.

Ir spectra of the complexes are similar to those observed earlier¹⁻⁶.

The above studies show that the mixed ligand complexes containing two different aromatic hydroxy ketones are formed.

However, the two ligands in the ternary complexes differ by only $-\text{CH}_2$ group, elemental analysis and tlc study may not precisely distinguish the formation of MLL' or ML₂. In order to confirm the formation of the mixed ligand complexes, further studies were carried out.

By nitration of hydroxy ketones (LH and L'H) two more ligands 3:5 dinitro 2-hydroxy acetophenone and 3:5 dinitro 2-hydroxy propiophenone were prepared. Above ligands were then used to prepare two mixed Schiff base complexes of Cu(II) (IV). The elemental results and TLC of above complexes clearly suggest that they are mixed Schiff base complexes. In case of mixed ligand complexes involving nitro compounds, there is a significant difference in the mol. wt. of the ternary and the binary compounds and hence analysis and TLC can definitely establish the formation of the mixed Schiff base complex. Hence the related Schiff base complex of Cu(II) derived by using 2-hydroxy acetophenone and 2-hydroxy propiophenone (I) should also be a mixed Schiff base complex.

The magnetic moments of complexes (IV) are ~ 1.8 and correspond to one unpaired electron. In the ir spectra the band corresponding to free $-\text{OH}$ group is absent but instead a band at ~ 3300 cm^{-1} corresponding to $-\text{N}-\text{H}$ stretch and a band at 1600 cm^{-1} corresponding to $-\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretch are present. Thus the ir spectra of above nitro complexes are similar to the mixed imine complex (I). Strong band at ~ 1500 cm^{-1} and ~ 1340 cm^{-1} correspond to asymmetric and symmetric stretch of $-\text{NO}_2$ groups, respectively. Further there is a broadening in bands in general and this indicates presence of $-\text{NO}_2$ group. Conductance measurements show that all complexes (I to IV) are non-electrolytes.

The formation of mixed Schiff base complex was further confirmed by demetallation technique. A single unsymmetrical Schiff base (V) was obtained whose analysis corresponds to the expected value.

The melting point of above unsymmetrical compound L₁L₂(V) was found to be different from those of the symmetrical Schiff bases L₁L₁ or L₂L₂. Also the tlc of the above unsymmetrical Schiff base gives a single spot different from above symmetrical Schiff bases.

The organic compound (V) isolated shows characteristic band at ~ 1600 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching mode but shows a shift of νOH to ~ 3000 cm^{-1} where it merges with C-H bands and is observed as a broad band. This is due to hydrogen bonding between two phenolic $-\text{OH}$ groups and also probably between nitrogen of imino group and hydrogen of $-\text{OH}$ groups.

Had the parent imine complex (I) been a mixture, the resulting tetradentate Schiff base complex (II) would have also been a mixture. This would have given a mixture of Schiff bases on demetallation. Isolation of a single unsymmetrical Schiff base clearly suggests that the parent imine Schiff base complex (I) and unsymmetrical tetradentate Schiff base complex (II) are pure and mixed ligand complexes. Incidentally this also provides a useful metal directed technique for the synthesis of unsymmetrical tetradentate Schiff bases which can not be prepared easily by the direct reaction.

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